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World Fuel Exports

Between 2010 and 2022 the average value of fuel exports decreased by -3.59% for the countries considered

The World Bank calculates the value of fuel exports as a percentage of global merchandise exports. Fuels include goods in section 3 of the SITC (mineral fuels, lubricants and related materials). The data refer to the period between 2010 and 2022. Only countries with a complete historical series in the considered period have been considered.

Ranking of countries by value of fuel exports as a percentage of global merchandise exports in 2022. Angola ranks first in value of fuel exports as a percentage of global merchandise exports in 2022 with a value equal to 94.92%, followed by Azerbaijan with a value of 92.54%, Qatar with 87.29%, Brunei Darussalam with 80.28%, and Norway with a value of 79.03%. In the middle of the table are Argentina with a value of 6.18%, followed by Denmark with a value of 5.97%, followed by France with a value of 5.35%, the Slovak Republic with 5.20%. from Malta with a value of 4.92%. The ranking is closed by French Polynesia with 0.03%, Fiji and Andorra with 0.01%, and Benin and Mauritius with 0.00%.

Ranking of countries by percent change in fuel export value between 2010 and 2022. Barbados ranks first in percent change in fuel export value with a value of 45,312.97%, followed by Niger with 1,741.71%, followed by Togo with 1,613.12%, the Dominican Republic with 994.01%, Mauritius with 440.71%. In the middle of the table are Kyrgyz Republic with 19.92%, followed by China with 5.89%, the United Kingdom with 0.05%, Azerbaijan with -2.09%, and the Slovak Republic with a value equal to -2.32%. Fiji closes the ranking with a value of -89.53%, followed by Hong Kong with -93.72%, Albania with -97.73%, Belize with -98.64%, and Bahrain with -99.94%. On average, the value of fuel exports as a percentage of goods exports decreased between 2010 and 2022 by an amount of -3.59% on average for the countries considered.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Elbow method. Below we present a clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Elbow method. The data show the presence of 4 different clusters. The clusters are indicated as below i.e.:

- *Cluster 1:* Belize, India, Singapore, Albania, Croatia, United States, Estonia, Netherlands, Bulgaria, Barbados, Brazil, South Africa, Bosnia and Herzegovina, United Kingdom, Belgium, Mexico, Finland, Togo, Kyrgyz Republic, Portugal, Sweden, Latvia, Denmark, Spain, Lebanon, French Polynesia, Fiji, Benin, Andorra, Dominican Republic, Rwanda, Mauritius, North Macedonia, Slovenia, Georgia, Moldova, Armenia, Uruguay, Jordan, Botswana, Ukraine, Luxembourg, Nicaragua, Argentina, Morocco, Hong Kong, Ireland, Namibia, Romania, Guatemala, Chile, Tanzania, Switzerland, Slovakia, Turkey, El Salvador, China, Iceland, New Zealand, Japan, Philippines, Germany, Italy, Poland, France, Hungary, Czech Republic, Austria.
- *Cluster 2:* Azerbaijan, Brunei Darussalam, Angola, Qatar;

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- *Cluster 3*: Norway, Kazakhstan, Bahrain;
- *Cluster 4*: Lithuania, Montenegro, Niger, Bolivia, Egypt, Mozambique, Paraguay, Malta, Canada, Myanmar, Australia, Greece.

From the point of view of the median, it appears that Cluster 2-C2 has a value of 89.91, followed by Cluster 3-C3 with a value of 61.38%, followed by Cluster 4-C4 with 29.39% and Cluster 1-C1 with an amount of 3.55%. The following ordering derives from it: $C2 > C3 > C4 > C1$. We can see that the dominant cluster or Cluster 2 is made up of countries whose essential asset is fuel exports. Angola stands out among the C2 countries with a very high value of fuel exports despite being a country with a very low per capita income equal to 1,953 dollars in 2021. Norway stands out in C3, however, which is the only western country with have significant percentages of fuels in their exports. The C4 countries follow, bringing together European, African, South American and Oceanian countries. Finally, there are the countries of cluster 1 among which there are many countries with high per capita incomes. It should be considered that the C1 countries have low values of fuel exports as a percentage of total exports both because they lack fuel supplies and because they have such a large export value that within exports the value of fuel is reduced.

Conclusions. From an economic point of view, we can see that the countries that are major fuel exporters are very heterogeneous among them. In fact, Azerbaijan, Brunei Darussalam, Angola, Qatar, Norway, Kazakhstan, Bahrain stands out. Fuel exports decreased marginally by an average value of -3.59% for the countries considered. It is probable that in the future the value of fuel exports will tend to decrease due to the orientation of the industrial system, especially in the West, towards energy sustainability. Certainly, the case of Norway is very particular, which has a very high level of fuel exports on total exports. In Norway in 2022 fuel exports as a percentage of total exports amounted to 79%. Since the value of Norwegian exports amounted to \$37.2 billion in 2022, then it follows that fuel exports to Norway in 2022 amounted to approximately \$29.38 billion. These are very important values that also raise questions relating to the ability of the Scandinavian country to be sustainable from an environmental point of view. However, among Western countries, Australia, Greece and Canada also had very high fuel export values in 2022 with values of 42.70%, 36.78%, and 32.50% respectively. It is likely that the application of green-oriented energy economic policies could depress the economies of Norway, Australia, Greece and Canada, which should find new types of exports to replace fuel exports. However, considering the significant economic interests of many countries, it is probable that the transition to a green economy is very expensive, especially for countries with low-medium per capita income or characterized by significant political-institutional instability.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Funding. The author received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

Acknowledgements. I am grateful to the teaching staff of the LUM University “Giuseppe Degennaro” and to the management of the LUM Enterprise s.r.l. for the constant inspiration to continue our scientific research work undeterred.

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Appendix

Plot of total within cluster squared distances (toy data)

Country Name	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Angola	97,91	98,14	98,37	98,22	97,72	94,02	92,70	94,69	95,67	95,25	93,05	94,16	94,92
Azerbaijan	94,51	94,75	93,42	93,00	92,76	88,46	91,70	90,60	91,74	90,65	87,25	88,41	92,54
Qatar	92,55	93,00	88,92	88,68	87,81	83,66	85,04	87,56	86,13	88,81	81,81	84,40	87,29
Brunei Darussalam	95,15	95,44	95,75	96,52	92,54	92,98	87,88	89,57	95,56	91,09	81,51	78,67	80,28
Norway	63,70	68,03	69,82	67,62	64,88	57,69	52,97	57,19	62,12	55,99	49,32	69,06	79,03
Kazakhstan	71,68	72,02	69,88	76,30	76,39	67,72	60,73	63,33	70,03	66,24	57,63	57,73	61,38
Mozambique	19,65	16,28	27,81	33,46	30,04	31,01	27,88	51,42	46,56	42,38	36,38	43,06	50,93
Australia	28,88	28,14	28,45	25,87	26,60	25,29	25,60	30,32	35,54	32,45	21,31	27,71	42,70
Egypt, Arab Rep.	28,68	29,25	30,13	26,08	23,36	17,87	13,77	19,35	24,57	26,50	17,62	32,34	37,33
Greece	26,08	30,85	38,95	39,88	38,45	29,80	27,49	31,52	34,33	31,55	21,87	28,20	36,78
Canada	25,32	27,43	25,62	26,36	28,89	20,60	17,63	21,95	24,02	24,08	19,33	25,87	32,50
Montenegro	10,76	14,98	13,83	29,01	14,54	14,81	16,09	12,38	20,81	21,41	16,65	18,52	29,97
Niger	1,56	1,11	18,28	30,20	27,03	18,78	16,46	13,19	14,41	25,65	14,70	37,78	28,81
Myanmar	35,18	35,91	24,36	33,62	42,78	44,52	28,16	26,81	21,93	25,11	20,52	21,32	23,49
Bolivia	43,27	45,36	50,01	54,54	51,74	46,15	31,17	33,25	34,85	32,07	29,47	21,48	22,73
India	17,23	18,76	18,78	20,67	19,63	11,87	10,64	12,19	15,07	13,78	10,03	14,28	21,75
United States	7,18	9,92	10,06	10,76	10,99	8,00	7,58	10,51	13,53	14,20	12,72	15,92	21,41
Belgium	10,37	12,19	13,03	13,31	11,41	8,79	6,43	7,25	8,57	7,38	5,02	8,82	20,14
Croatia	12,47	12,08	13,67	13,99	13,51	10,90	9,49	10,71	10,56	9,48	9,04	11,87	19,39
Brazil	9,90	10,56	11,02	7,66	9,35	7,36	6,45	8,71	12,77	13,71	11,89	13,66	17,00
Paraguay	30,49	29,33	31,02	23,97	22,69	25,05	25,40	24,77	23,32	20,50	20,40	15,25	16,79
Lithuania	23,35	25,29	24,50	23,04	17,55	16,31	13,77	14,78	14,60	13,13	6,91	9,86	16,76
South Africa	10,71	10,54	11,42	10,70	10,18	9,75	9,83	12,01	10,99	10,05	8,11	8,68	14,33
Netherlands	10,16	12,79	14,46	14,43	12,57	10,25	9,15	10,28	10,74	10,65	7,46	9,01	13,65

Estonia	15,76	16,76	16,13	10,23	11,08	10,96	8,26	9,91	6,25	5,15	10,68	6,84	12,78
Singapore	16,06	19,45	18,18	17,00	16,53	12,19	11,07	12,81	13,12	12,26	8,09	10,04	12,75
Latvia	5,31	8,26	7,84	7,70	8,65	7,46	5,69	5,24	5,24	4,54	3,57	5,90	12,40
United Kingdom	12,37	12,62	13,87	11,42	10,90	7,02	6,26	7,97	9,46	8,60	7,06	8,33	12,38
Bulgaria	13,29	13,13	16,17	14,73	12,60	10,62	9,01	9,91	8,89	9,53	4,64	6,00	12,19
Finland	8,01	9,49	10,92	12,22	10,77	6,76	7,67	7,87	8,48	8,94	7,01	7,00	10,44
Sweden	6,98	7,31	9,38	7,85	8,08	6,18	5,65	6,43	7,43	6,36	4,54	6,95	10,17
Bosnia and Herzegovina	15,09	13,97	8,96	11,38	9,60	7,01	6,80	8,36	9,78	8,09	6,74	8,54	9,98
Barbados	0,02	7,37	10,80	9,10	9,34	5,53	3,53	5,20	4,63	28,70	4,78	4,66	9,76
Kyrgyz Republic	7,42	10,02	12,22	10,78	7,61	5,22	3,44	4,96	7,59	6,04	4,38	3,63	8,90
Spain	5,22	6,35	7,66	7,07	7,49	5,17	4,07	5,83	6,56	6,17	4,05	6,01	8,75
Portugal	6,41	7,17	8,32	10,41	8,36	7,66	6,25	7,17	6,89	6,09	4,60	5,77	8,43
Slovenia	4,23	5,74	6,45	6,64	6,14	5,31	4,51	4,90	5,21	5,30	3,06	4,11	8,03
Euro area	5,23	6,22	6,75	6,57	5,92	4,81	3,96	4,59	5,02	4,75	3,41	4,76	7,74
Romania	5,30	5,50	5,53	5,21	5,99	4,46	3,60	3,77	4,10	3,78	2,42	3,52	7,63
Mexico	13,77	15,95	14,06	12,81	10,41	5,89	4,82	5,51	6,57	5,32	3,84	5,54	6,52
Turkiye	3,84	4,75	4,90	6,11	4,37	3,26	2,14	2,75	3,12	4,49	2,69	3,69	6,32
Argentina	7,90	5,97	6,23	4,68	4,68	2,54	2,50	2,79	4,12	3,60	2,68	2,64	6,18
Denmark	8,07	8,91	9,36	8,57	6,55	4,83	3,52	3,96	4,31	3,99	2,08	4,44	5,97
France	3,66	4,54	4,45	3,91	3,88	2,96	2,31	2,80	3,29	2,78	1,88	3,19	5,35
Slovak Republic	5,32	6,34	5,93	5,50	4,50	3,57	2,74	3,34	3,02	2,91	2,40	3,20	5,20
Malta	25,58	42,48	45,08	42,44	43,04	38,45	25,37	37,79	31,00	28,84	3,16	7,27	4,92
El Salvador	2,92	3,18	3,18	2,31	2,57	1,96	2,86	3,17	3,54	3,37	3,21	3,89	4,79
Italy	4,64	4,76	4,70	4,28	3,74	3,29	2,66	3,27	3,47	3,05	2,14	3,10	4,51
North Macedonia	7,68	8,71	6,44	2,48	1,75	1,36	1,15	1,50	1,70	2,04	1,41	1,83	4,39
Hungary	2,66	3,49	4,04	3,60	3,34	2,30	1,82	2,50	2,81	2,62	2,19	3,20	4,33
Poland	4,15	4,90	5,00	4,70	4,14	3,31	2,55	2,55	2,60	2,24	1,58	2,21	3,98
Germany	1,97	2,30	2,44	2,42	2,25	2,13	1,64	1,80	2,06	2,22	1,82	2,60	3,61
Czechia	3,68	3,78	3,78	2,96	2,65	2,94	1,87	1,79	1,93	1,72	1,20	2,22	3,55
Namibia	1,27	1,29	0,95	1,24	1,46	2,64	1,32	0,44	0,58	0,75	0,75	1,35	3,30
Austria	3,21	3,38	3,66	2,70	2,39	1,96	1,69	1,90	2,09	2,22	1,94	2,47	3,13
Tanzania	1,90	0,76	1,25	2,25	1,67	2,20	0,87	1,13	0,89	0,82	0,82	0,91	3,09
Guatemala	4,52	5,08	3,96	4,61	6,54	4,12	3,19	3,46	4,18	4,55	2,36	2,71	2,89
Georgia	5,03	4,13	2,95	3,27	3,77	8,14	3,43	4,10	1,97	0,72	0,38	0,79	2,64
Switzerland	2,82	3,11	2,34	1,02	1,11	0,95	0,62	0,69	0,94	0,81	0,61	1,13	2,46
Japan	1,70	1,98	1,68	2,33	2,29	1,82	1,45	1,63	1,81	1,99	1,19	1,35	2,44
Ukraine	7,12	8,32	5,30	4,53	3,73	1,28	1,23	1,82	1,82	1,72	1,13	1,13	2,35
Iceland	1,03	1,93	2,01	1,60	1,99	1,61	1,31	1,18	2,01	1,59	0,72	1,15	2,32
Armenia	3,02	7,93	7,45	5,74	5,94	5,92	3,49	3,58	3,73	2,85	3,00	1,84	1,81
China	1,69	1,70	1,51	1,53	1,47	1,23	1,28	1,56	1,87	1,87	1,21	1,24	1,79
Chile	1,10	1,30	1,28	1,38	1,27	0,90	0,90	1,06	1,18	1,00	0,68	0,82	1,73
Togo	0,10	0,72	1,84	1,00	1,39	1,44	1,90	8,29	13,03	15,29	2,36	2,48	1,71
New Zealand	4,94	5,49	4,93	3,72	3,23	1,90	1,46	1,67	1,81	1,45	1,10	1,19	1,65
Philippines	2,05	2,92	2,43	3,77	2,97	1,32	1,33	1,51	1,70	1,48	1,09	1,18	1,57
Uruguay	3,10	0,74	1,09	0,49	1,11	0,29	0,48	2,00	1,19	1,09	1,24	5,65	1,50
Dominican Republic	0,10	2,93	6,34	1,96	5,70	4,41	3,83	4,70	5,08	4,37	0,32	0,77	1,09
Morocco	3,31	4,34	5,76	7,22	5,07	1,93	0,85	0,92	1,17	1,51	0,52	0,69	1,01

Jordan	1,08	0,18	0,28	0,17	0,17	0,12	0,10	0,12	1,71	2,03	1,33	0,71	0,95
Ireland	1,13	1,45	1,76	0,92	0,91	0,69	0,58	0,81	0,73	0,58	0,48	0,57	0,86
Moldova	0,34	0,69	0,31	0,19	0,25	0,13	0,06	0,06	0,05	0,02	0,07	0,08	0,84
Nicaragua	1,23	0,68	1,10	0,43	0,31	0,28	0,16	0,23	0,26	0,30	0,44	0,60	0,82
Botswana	0,18	0,67	0,98	0,68	0,72	0,50	0,17	0,15	0,19	0,29	0,39	0,39	0,71
Belize	37,19	44,56	27,46	20,97	16,67	6,83	5,65	5,15	6,27	4,94	1,34	1,97	0,51
Lebanon	0,13	0,10	2,02	8,56	0,98	0,81	0,48	0,49	0,84	1,45	0,34	0,24	0,43
Albania	17,96	21,18	26,59	30,99	1,57	8,81	11,18	0,82	1,66	0,60	0,91	0,02	0,41
Luxembourg	0,95	0,82	0,91	0,91	0,79	0,48	0,06	0,09	0,10	0,10	0,08	0,16	0,21
Hong Kong SAR, China	1,97	2,05	1,08	1,08	1,44	1,81	0,88	0,11	0,12	0,12	0,09	0,10	0,12
Rwanda	0,07	0,04	0,02	0,11	0,20	0,13	0,07	0,08	0,32	1,91	0,04	0,05	0,06
Bahrain	74,35	71,84	64,15	59,00	66,83	50,36	45,02	50,18	53,32	42,13	29,82	0,05	0,04
French Polynesia	0,04	0,03	0,01	0,02	0,01	0,00	0,01	0,03	0,01	0,03	0,22	0,06	0,03
Fiji	0,09	0,12	0,04	0,03	0,01	0,00	0,02	0,05	0,04	0,02	0,01	0,02	0,01
Andorra	0,00	0,00	0,10	0,13	0,11	0,04	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,09	0,03	0,03	0,01
Benin	0,01	0,11	0,01	0,00	0,25	0,01	0,05	0,03	0,00	0,02	0,01	0,00	0,00
Mauritius	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	1,56	1,10	0,93	0,29	0,00	0,00

Rank	Country Name	2022	Rank	Country Name	2022
1	Angola	94,92	45	Slovak Republic	5,20
2	Azerbaijan	92,54	46	Malta	4,92
3	Qatar	87,29	47	El Salvador	4,79
4	Brunei Darussalam	80,28	48	Italy	4,51
5	Norway	79,03	49	North Macedonia	4,39
6	Kazakhstan	61,38	50	Hungary	4,33
7	Mozambique	50,93	51	Poland	3,98
8	Australia	42,70	52	Germany	3,61
9	Egypt, Arab Rep.	37,33	53	Czechia	3,55
10	Greece	36,78	54	Namibia	3,30
11	Canada	32,50	55	Austria	3,13
12	Montenegro	29,97	56	Tanzania	3,09
13	Niger	28,81	57	Guatemala	2,89
14	Myanmar	23,49	58	Georgia	2,64
15	Bolivia	22,73	59	Switzerland	2,46
16	India	21,75	60	Japan	2,44
17	United States	21,41	61	Ukraine	2,35
18	Belgium	20,14	62	Iceland	2,32
19	Croatia	19,39	63	Armenia	1,81
20	Brazil	17,00	64	China	1,79
21	Paraguay	16,79	65	Chile	1,73
22	Lithuania	16,76	66	Togo	1,71
23	South Africa	14,33	67	New Zealand	1,65
24	Netherlands	13,65	68	Philippines	1,57

25	Estonia	12,78	69	Uruguay	1,50
26	Singapore	12,75	70	Dominican Republic	1,09
27	Latvia	12,40	71	Morocco	1,01
28	United Kingdom	12,38	72	Jordan	0,95
29	Bulgaria	12,19	73	Ireland	0,86
30	Finland	10,44	74	Moldova	0,84
31	Sweden	10,17	75	Nicaragua	0,82
32	Bosnia and Herzegovina	9,98	76	Botswana	0,71
33	Barbados	9,76	77	Belize	0,51
34	Kyrgyz Republic	8,90	78	Lebanon	0,43
35	Spain	8,75	79	Albania	0,41
36	Portugal	8,43	80	Luxembourg	0,21
37	Slovenia	8,03	81	Hong Kong SAR, China	0,12
38	Euro area	7,74	82	Rwanda	0,06
39	Romania	7,63	83	Bahrain	0,04
40	Mexico	6,52	84	French Polynesia	0,03
41	Turkiye	6,32	85	Fiji	0,01
42	Argentina	6,18	86	Andorra	0,01
43	Denmark	5,97	87	Benin	0,00
44	France	5,35	88	Mauritius	0,00

Rank	Country Name	Var Per	Rank	Country Name	Var Per
1	Barbados	45312,97	45	Azerbaijan	-2,09
2	Niger	1741,71	46	Slovak Republic	-2,32
3	Togo	1613,12	47	Austria	-2,56
4	Dominican Republic	994,01	48	Italy	-2,78
5	Mauritius	440,71	49	Angola	-3,05
6	Botswana	285,47	50	Czechia	-3,59
7	Lebanon	227,39	51	Poland	-4,1
8	Andorra	225,63	52	Qatar	-5,69
9	United States	198	53	Bulgaria	-8,27
10	Montenegro	178,68	54	Rwanda	-8,66
11	Namibia	159,8	55	French Polynesia	-9,68
12	Mozambique	159,12	56	Jordan	-11,86
13	Moldova	149,94	57	Switzerland	-12,66
14	Latvia	133,72	58	Kazakhstan	-14,36
15	Iceland	125,17	59	Brunei Darussalam	-15,63
16	Belgium	94,1	60	Estonia	-18,86
17	Slovenia	89,71	61	Singapore	-20,62
18	Germany	83,51	62	Argentina	-21,84
19	Brazil	71,69	63	Philippines	-23,62
20	Spain	67,64	64	Ireland	-23,79

21	Turkiye	64,79	65	Denmark	-25,99
22	El Salvador	63,91	66	Lithuania	-28,2
23	Hungary	63,16	67	Myanmar	-33,22
24	Tanzania	62,3	68	Nicaragua	-33,55
25	Chile	56,77	69	Bosnia and Herzegovina	-33,86
26	Croatia	55,52	70	Guatemala	-36,03
27	Euro area	47,89	71	Armenia	-39,96
28	Australia	47,83	72	North Macedonia	-42,85
29	France	46,15	73	Paraguay	-44,93
30	Sweden	45,64	74	Bolivia	-47,47
31	Japan	44,18	75	Georgia	-47,63
32	Romania	44,03	76	Uruguay	-51,62
33	Greece	41,05	77	Mexico	-52,66
34	Netherlands	34,33	78	New Zealand	-66,73
35	South Africa	33,77	79	Ukraine	-66,99
36	Portugal	31,57	80	Benin	-68,98
37	Finland	30,33	81	Morocco	-69,5
38	Egypt, Arab Rep.	30,17	82	Luxembourg	-77,47
39	Canada	28,32	83	Malta	-80,76
40	India	26,25	84	Fiji	-89,53
41	Norway	24,07	85	Hong Kong SAR, China	-93,72
42	Kyrgyz Republic	19,92	86	Albania	-97,73
43	China	5,89	87	Belize	-98,64
44	United Kingdom	0,05	88	Bahrain	-99,94